

Studies on Isoxazolones. Part III. Formation Constants of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) Complexes of Dimethyl Diisoxazolone

NRIPENDRA NATH GHOSH* and PARESH CHANDRA CHOUDHURY

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009
and

Department of Chemistry, M. B. B. College, Agartala, Tripura

Manuscript received 30 March 1976; accepted 15 June 1976

A potentiometric study on the complex formation of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) with dimethyl diisoxazolone (RH) in (1 : 1) water-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) at $31 \pm 0.5^\circ$, has been made. The successive formation constants K_1 and K_2 have been determined following Irving and Rossotti method. $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are computed by graphical methods and are found to be 1.72, 1.61; 1.61, 1.23 for Cu(II) and UO₂(II) respectively. The acid dissociation constant k^* of RH has also been determined in (1 : 1) water-dioxan as well as in (1 : 1) water-methanol are found to be $\text{pk}^* = 2.88$ and 2.40 respectively.

IN our previous communication¹ the preparation of some complex compounds (MR_2) of dimethyl diisoxazolone (RH) and their various physico-chemical properties are reported. The present communication describes the determination of formation constants of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) complexes of RH following Irving and Rossotti titration technique² in (1 : 1) water-dioxan at $31^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ in presence of requisite amount of NaClO₄ to maintain ionic strength constant ($\mu = 0.5$).

Formation of MR^+ and MR_2^0 complexes are indicated. Acid dissociation constant of the ligand RH has been determined under identical conditions and also in (1 : 1) water-methanol.

Experimental

The ligand RH was prepared by condensing ethyl acetoacetate with hydroxylamine³ and purified as stated in our earlier communication¹. All other reagents were either of AR quality or properly purified. The solutions were made in doubly distilled water and purified dioxan⁴.

The measurement of pH of the solutions was made with a Cambridge Portable Type pH-Meter

using a glass electrode or 1-13 pH range in conjunction with SCE connected to the cell by means of an agar-2M NaNO₃ bridge. The pH-meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions in water with due temperature corrections.

Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml solutions in (1 : 1) water-dioxan of the following composition: (a) 0.03M HClO₄; (b) 0.03M HClO₄+0.03M RH; (c) 0.03M HClO₄+0.03M RH+0.01M or 0.005M metal perchlorate, with a 0.15M NaOH solution in (1 : 1) water-dioxan. The ionic strength of the media was kept constant ($\mu = 0.05$) throughout by adding requisite amount of NaClO₄. Duplicate titrations were made under identical conditions. Titration curves i.e., pH vs. volume of alkali solution added, were plotted.

Results

The stepwise formation of metal complexes may be represented as

From the titration curves the average number ($\bar{n}_H$) of protons associated with the ligand ion, the average number ($\bar{n}$) of ligand ion R⁻ bound to metal ions, and free ligand exponent pR_0 , where $\text{R}_0 = [\text{R}^-]$, were calculated using the expressions (3), (4) and (5) respectively of Irving and Rossotti².

$$\bar{n}_H = y - \frac{(v'' - v')(N^0 + E^0)}{(v^0 + v')T_L} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v''' - v'')[N^0 + E^0 + T_L(y - \bar{n}_H)]}{(v^0 + v'')\bar{n}_H T_M} \quad \dots (4)$$

* Senior author.

$$pR_0 = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n-2} \beta_n H \left(\frac{1}{\text{anti log } B} \right)^n}{T_L - \bar{n} T_M} \times \frac{v^\circ + v'''}{v^\circ} \right] \dots$$

where v' , v'' and v''' are the volumes of alkali solution required to reach the same pH i.e., same pH-meter reading B in the titrations of (a), (b) and (c) solutions respectively; v° , T_L , T_M and E° are the initial volume of the mixture, initial concentrations of the ligand RH, metal ion and HClO_4 respectively; N° is the concentration of alkali; y is the number of dissociable protons and equal to one in the present case.

The acid dissociation constant (k^*) has been obtained by linear plot of the equation (6).

$$\text{pH} = \log \frac{1 - \bar{n}_H}{\bar{n}_H} + pk^* \dots (6)$$

The standard deviation (σ) have been calculated⁵ employing the relation (7)

$$\sigma = \pm \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta \bar{n}_H)^2}{N} \right]^{1/2} \dots (7)$$

where N = number of observations and $\Delta \bar{n}_H = \bar{n}_{H(\text{expt.})} - \bar{n}_{H(\text{calc.})}$. $\bar{n}_{H(\text{calc.})}$ values are obtained from the relation (8) using experimentally determined k^*

$$\bar{n}_{H(\text{calc.})} = \frac{1}{1 + k^*/[H^+]} \dots (8)$$

Results are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF LIGAND RH

Solvent	pk*	Standard deviation (Range)
(1 : 1) water-dioxan	2.88 ± 0.03	± 0.008 (0.2 < n < 1.0)
(1 : 1) water-methanol	2.40 ± 0.03	± 0.008 (0 < n < 0.8)

By plotting $\bar{n}$ vs pR_0 , formation curves have been obtained. The nature of formation curves indicates overlapping of the complex formation steps and consequently the successive formation constants K_1 and K_2 have been evaluated by linear plots of the equation (9)

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(1 - \bar{n})R_0} = \frac{(2 - \bar{n})R_0}{(1 - \bar{n})} K_1 K_2 + K_1 \dots (9)$$

The $\bar{n}$ values have been calculated from equation (10) using experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2 .

$$\bar{n}_{(\text{calc.})} = \frac{K_1 R_0 + 2K_1 K_2 R_0^2}{1 + K_1 R_0 + K_1 K_2 R_0^2} \dots (10)$$

The calculated formation curves have been drawn along with the experimental points. Standard deviation (σ) has also been calculated⁵. Limits of error have been found out by comparing the experimental formation curves with the calculated ones⁵. Results are stated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES

Metal complexes	log K_1	log K_2	Standard deviation (Range)
Cu(II)	1.72 ± 0.03	1.61 ± 0.03	± 0.008 (0.1 < n < 0.9)
UO ₂ (II)	1.61 ± 0.04	1.23 ± 0.04	± 0.013 (0.1 < n < 0.6)

Discussion

The pk^* value of the ligand RH as determined in (1 : 1) water-dioxan is found to be 2.88 and in (1 : 1) water-methanol the corresponding pk^* value is 2.40. This observation is in accordance with much more polar character of water-methanol mixture than that of water-dioxan one. As indicated by pk^* values, RH appears to be an acid of moderate strength. Any plausible explanation could not be offered in support of this anomalous acidic characteristic of RH.

The ligand RH appears to behave as a bidentate one and form chelates with Cu(II) and UO₂(II). Their stability constant values indicate that they are weak complexes, which is also supported by the conductance data¹. During titrations of metal ions in presence of ligand and free HClO_4 , with a NaOH solution, precipitation occurred earlier and as a result, $\bar{n} > 1$ could not be calculated. The stability order is found to be Cu(II) > UO₂(II) as expected.

Possibilities of the formation of polynuclear species have been checked by using the different concentrations (0.01M and 0.005M) of metal ions with the same concentration (0.03M) of ligand. The coincidence of the experimental points on the same calculated curves supports the formation of mononuclear complexes only. With Ni(II) and Co(II), similar potentiometric studies were made, but no proof of complex formation with RH, was obtained.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

References

1. N. N. GHOSH and P. C. CHOUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 439.
2. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
3. R. E. ROSE and W. SCOTT, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 273.
3. A. I. VOGEL, in "A Text-book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1968, p. 177.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
6. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, in "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, London, 1961, p. 88.